

MOTHER TONGUE EDUCATION AT SECONDARY SPECIAL LEVEL

¹Yusupova Tursunoi Akhmedovna, ²Karaeva Begam Kholmanovna

¹Associate professor of TashSULLU named after Alisher Navoi, Candidate of pedagogical sciences

²Professor of Moscow State University of Linguistics, Doctor of pedagogic sciences

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Abstract. *The article analyzes how to teach students in their native language at professional schools. It will analyze the ways to teach with strategies and examples which are suitable to the theories that will be discussed below.*

Keywords: *professional school, teaching the mother tongue, the goal of teaching the mother tongue, the development of professional creative thinking.*

We know that students' cognitive activity develops dynamically. Taking this into account, it is necessary that the general and specific goals of education, specific to specific educational subjects, are reflected in the content of education. One of the important conditions that ensure that the content of the education is in accordance with the educational goal is the system of educational activities that encourage students to be independent and think freely in the educational process, each subject in the educational process, each type of activity, each lesson and a set of educational tasks designed for the student to complete in a specific lesson. , everything, that is, the entire educational system should serve to realize the main goal, to set and implement the task of engaging in mental, logical activity.

The student will be complete only if the educational content reflects the political, economic, spiritual, cultural, educational life, people's way of life, mentality of the society, which strives to occupy a worthy place in the future. In order for the student to take a proper place in the life style of this nation and society, he must adapt and be ready for it.

According to the nature of secondary special vocational education, it provides its graduate with secondary special vocational education within the framework of the relevant state educational standards; It allows students to deepen their professional inclination, knowledge and skills, and acquire one or more specialties in the chosen profession.

Secondary special educational institutions are new type of educational institutions in terms of the level of equipment, the selection of pedagogical content, and the organization of the educational process. They allow to master one or several modern professions and to get deep theoretical knowledge from relevant academic subjects.

Secondary special education provides students with the opportunity to deepen their knowledge and acquire a chosen specialty, and its graduates are awarded state-approved model diplomas. These diplomas give the right to continue studying at the next stages of education or to work in the acquired specialty and profession.

The demands and needs, opportunities and tasks of mother tongue education at the secondary special level are connected, first of all, with ensuring the balance between the purpose of education and its content. The goal of education and the content of education determined in proportion to it is a didactic phenomenon that is continuously developing and updating, and this process is created in connection with social reality. According to the principle of conformity of

educational content with its purpose, the content of a specific educational subject, including mother tongue education, should be in accordance with its goals, the size, scale, language construction, educational goals, and student's capabilities. This law is explained by the fact that at each stage, the content of education, which is comprehensible for students in every way, the volume of the presented educational material, its technological construction should consist of words and terms necessary for students from the point of view of specialization. However, the size, content, language construction and expression technology of the educational materials selected for a certain stage are variable rather than regular. As a result of the acceleration of social development, the increase of socio-pedagogical factors that affect the members of society, including the personality of the student, the development process of students accelerates. Their worldview, thinking, language skills develop regularly under the influence of a number of socio-pedagogical factors. At the same time, the content of education determined on the basis of standards that have fallen into a mold does not correspond to the educational goals and is far from the needs and possibilities of the student. For example, at the current stage of developing market economy relations, independence, economic and legal freedom had a positive effect on the development of the social consciousness of society members. The expansion of information banks in the content of textbooks and educational literature allows students' minds to be enriched with many new concepts and information. After all, one of such standards is to look at the personality of the student as a subject of the educational process [1].

Only when the educational content is selected in accordance with its purpose, it serves to ensure the effectiveness of the educational result, the intellectual development of students. It should not be forgotten that not any educational process, but only the educational process aimed at developing the student's creative and independent activity skills, can serve to ensure the intellectual development of students, creative independent thinking. Activity in the educational process, including accurate acquisition of language tools, is largely related to the individual needs of a person (student). For example, the level of "Lexicology", i.e., "Word Studies", which is taught to students in secondary general education schools, is also taught in secondary special education. (True, the topics are not exactly repeated: their use (for example, the style of terms, the style of professional words, the style of obsolete words, etc.) is taught.)

At this point, if the teacher lacks creativity, the student is limited to repeating what he learned in secondary general education and completing the tasks given in the textbook. Naturally, a teacher who is a creative thinker has a different approach to the issue. Let's say that a teacher of a native language course in a medical college uses the following learning tasks in passing "Terminology Methodology":

Task 1. Give examples of medical terms and explain their meanings.

For the second task, students are divided into small groups such as 4x4, 5x5 or 6x6 (depending on the number of students in the class). (It is advisable for them to sit in a circle to complete the task.) The teacher gives each small group separate but similar educational tasks. For example,

In subgroup 1: Write the names of painkillers (in pill form).

In subgroup 2: Write the names of painkillers (in the form of ampoules).

In subgroup 3: Write the names of painkillers (ointment; ointment).

In subgroup 4: Write the names of painkillers (injected into the flesh).

In sub-group 5: Write the names of pain-relieving (intravenous) drugs.

In subgroup 6: Write the names of painkillers (both in pill and ampoule form).

It is also possible to give the form of the assignment with a slight change. In this case, students are presented with tables with the names of at least fifty or sixty drugs (for example, aspirin, anoperine, demidrol, analgin, trimol, senipar, baralgin, heparin, dibazol, enam, enap, norsulfazol, sulfazol, etc.) execution is also useful.

Or–

For example, when teaching the topic "Hives and their methodological features" at a medical school, a student may be given the following task:

Task 1. Continue the given lines.

"Medicine" slot

- 1) drop drugs (dibazol, analgin, demidrol.....)
 - a) drop drugs administered to the patient only intravenously: (calcium gluconate,.....)
 - b) drop drugs administered to the patient only through the skin: (.....)
 - d) drop drugs that can be administered to the patient both through the skin and intravenously: (.....)
- 2) tablets (citramon, trimol, sulgin, tetracycline,)
 - a) painkillers: (sinipar,...)
 - b) medical tablets: (ampicillin, ...)
- 3) medicines in the form of both drops and tablets: (analgin, demidrol, ferrumlik,...)
- 4) ointments: (vasilene, glycerin,...)
 - a) drugs for back pain: (.....)
 - b) medicines applied for leg pain: (.....)
 - d) drugs for eye pain: (.....)
 - e) drugs for neck pain: (.....)

These lines can be continued with headache pills, stomach pain pills, heart pain pills, energy pills, or first aid shots.

It is also appropriate to recommend test samples in the following content:

Test samples

1. Lubricants: vaseline, glycerin, senipar gel, star, iodine, tetracycline, alcohol. Find the foreign word in the given group.
 - A) Asterisk *B) tetracycline C) glycerin D) senipar gel
2. Tablets: citramon, trimol, sulgin, tetracycline, glycerin, senipar, analgin, calcium gluconate. Find the foreign word in the given slot.
 - A) calcium gluconate B) sulgin *C) glycerin D) senipar
3. Head diseases: meningitis, tumor, stroke, otitis. Find the foreign word in the given slot.
 - *A) otitis B) stroke C) tumor D) meningitis
4. Medicinal tablets: ampicillin, baralgin, trichopol, analgin, potassium aortate. Find the foreign word in the given slot.
 - A) Trichopol B) Ampicillin C) Potassium aortate *D) Analgin
5. Painkillers: tablets: demedrol, analgin, trimol, tetracycline, aspirin, paracetamol, no-spa, glucose. Find the foreign word in the given slot.
 - A) trimol B) tetracycline *C) glucose D) analgen
6. Therapist-cardiologist-ortologist-stomatologist-surgeon-gynecologist-urologist-pharmacist-psychologist-diphtologist-psychotherapist-endocrinologist. Find the name of the cardiologist from the given slot.

- A) Therapist B) gynecologist C) otorhinolaryngology *D) cardiologist
7. Therapist-cardiologist-lor-stomatologist-surgeon-gynecologist-urologist-pharmacist-psychologist-diphtologist-psychotherapist-endocrinologist. Find the name of the kidney doctor from the given slot.
- A) Therapist B) gynecologist *C) urologist D) diphtong
8. Therapist-cardiologist-lor-stomatologist-surgeon-gynecologist-urologist-pharmacist-psychologist-diphtologist-psychotherapist-endocrinologist. Find the name of the gynecologist from the given slot.
- A) Therapist *B) gynecologist C) endocrinologist D) diphtologist
9. Therapist-cardiologist-lor-stomatologist-surgeon-gynecologist-urologist-pharmacist-psychologist-diphtologist-psychotherapist-endocrinologist. Find the name of the mumps doctor from the given slot.
- A) Therapist B) stomotologist *C) endocrinologist D) diphtologist
10. Therapist-cardiologist-lor-stomatologist-surgeon-gynecologist-urologist-pharmacist-psychologist-phthologist-psychotherapist-endocrinologist. Find the name of the internal medicine doctor in the given slot.
- *A) therapist B) stomotologist C) endocrinologist D) diphtologist
11. Tuberculosis-bod-bronchitis-asthma-jaundice-anemia-diabetes-stomatitis-angina-meningitis-burcellosis-goiter. Find the name of liver disease from the given slot.
- A) Tuberculosis B) hangover *C) jaundice D) stomatitis
12. Thermometer-tweezers-scissors-tonometer-phonendoscope-endoscope-probe-catheter-electric suction-brucellosis. Which of the following is not a medical device?
- A) Tonometer B) endoscope *C) brucellosis D) probe
13. Thermometer-tweezers-scissors-tonometer-phonendoscope-endoscope-probe-catheter-electric suction-medical hammer. Which medical device from the given slot is usually used by a neurologist?
- A) catheter B) phonendoscope *C) medical hammer D) electric suction
14. Band-aid-medical cotton-syringe-alcohol-system-probe. Which of the following is not a tool used in emergency medical care?
- A) bandage B) system *C) probe D) bandage
15. Calcium chloride-nasathir--insulin-brilliant blue-analgesics-broncholytic-antibiotic-iodine-medical hammer. Which of the given slots is not included in the Msira of emergency medical equipment? *A) medical hammer B) diamond blue C) iodine D) drug
16. Ketanol, dibazol, aspirin-P, no-shpa, glucose, sodium chloride, heparin, caffeine, lidocaine. Which of the given cells is a saline solution?
- A) Glucose B) lidocaine C) heparin *D) sodium chloride
17. Ketanol, dibazol, aspirin-P, no-shpa, glucose, sodium chloride, heparin, caffeine, lidocaine. Which of the given cells is a sugar medium?
- *A) glucose B) lidocaine C) heparin D) sodium chloride
18. Ketanol, dibazol, aspirin-P, no-shpa, glucose, sodium chloride, heparin, caffeine, lidocaine. Which of the following is an anti-inflammatory agent?
- *A) Ketanol B) Lidocaine C) Heparin D) Sodium chloride
19. Ketanol, dibazol, aspirin-P, no-shpa, glucose, sodium chloride, heporin, caffeine, ascorbin, novocaine, lidocaine. Which of the given cells belongs to the group of vitamin C?

*A) ascorbin B) lidocaine C) heporin D) novocaine

20. Corvalol, validol, barboval, lidocaine. Which of the following is an essential oil agent?

*A) validol B) lidocaine C) corvalol D) barboval

Completing and analyzing such educational tasks in native language classes for a student learning a profession, firstly, creates interdisciplinary connections, and secondly, forms and develops specialized creative thinking in the student.

It can be seen that in order to ensure the compatibility of teaching tools with the purpose of education, in the course of the lesson, the student should be given educational tasks that match his needs and capabilities. It is important to ensure that such assignments form the basis of the curriculum. The results of a careful study of the students' thinking range and level of speech fluency show that during the educational process, when a student is given the task of solving one or another problem, "Is the setting of such a problem in accordance with the purpose of education?" From the didactic point of view, there should always be a positive answer to the question. The solution of the problem presented to the student should encourage him to think, to think independently and to draw logical conclusions in certain situations. That's how we will help to improve the professional qualification of the student of the vocational college.

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